

PLANTS GROWTH SUBSTANCES PRODUCED BY BACTERIA

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This paper will discuss about the application of an interdisciplinary biological field, between microbiology and plant physiology. Microbiology is the study of microorganisms, which are unicellular organisms that too small to be seen with the naked eye and only can be seen with microscopes. This includes eukaryotes (organisms with a nucleus), such as fungi, and prokaryotes (organisms without a nucleus), such as bacteria and viruses. The microbiological study gave a basic understanding of microbes at the level of the cell, protein and genes, microbial growth, also at the level of the community (ecology and epidemiology). Recently, microbiology is widely developed in various fields of science, like agriculture, industry, health, the environment, the food sector, and even the space sector (Waluyo, 2009). The use of microbes in the industrial sector has been widely used, such as in the chemical industry, medicine and the food industry. One of the products of microbes in the industrial sector is a growth substance, this growth substance is produced by bacteria. To determine the ability of growth substances produced by bacteria, the scientific field of plant physiology is needed to see the effect of growth substances given to plants. Plant physiology encompasses the study of plant form and function. It includes the study of such topics in plant biology as metabolic processes and activities of plants in maintaining and regulating their life (Advinda, 2018).

Plant growth substance is non-nutritive organic compounds that in low concentrations can encourage, inhibit or change the quality of plant growth and development. One of the growth substances that are often used is Gibberellin (GA₃) which has many roles in influencing plant physiological processes (Maharani, 2018). ZPT is divided into two types, that is natural growth regulators and synthetic growth regulators. Synthetic growth regulators are growth regulators from chemicals such as NAA, IAA, IBA, which are included in auxins and BAP, Kinetin which is included in Cytokinins. Natural growth regulators produced by the plants themselves such as auxins, cytokinins and gibberellins (Dwi, 2020). PGR is needed by plants as a medium for growth and development. Hormones in plants can be produced from the individual itself (endogenous hormones) or can be given from outside the individual (exogenous hormones) (Asra, 2020). Research conducted by Apriliani (2015) showed that the addition of several types of auxin to shoots of bayur cuttings did not show a significant effect. This was due to the sufficient endogenous auxin contained in these plants so that exogenous auxin administration would not affect root formation. Conversely, if the cutting material is in a condition lacking endogenous PGR, then the success of the cutting is largely determined by the addition of exogenous PGR (Harsanto, 1999).

Currently, plant growth is enhanced by the input of chemicals that act as plant growth regulators (using a hormonal mechanism) and as nutrients. The high input of chemicals raises several concerns such as water contamination leading to eutrophication and health risks for humans. It's also causing soil degradation and loss of biodiversity (Ben, 2018). This paper wants to discuss about beneficial microbes which can act as environmentally friendly alternatives for agrochemicals and their application will increase the sustainability of agriculture.

Bacteria were mostly regarded as either pathogens or irrelevant to host function. However, the growing field of microbial research, studying the communities of bacteria residing within the genes they contain has yielded new perspectives. Surprisingly, commensal bacteria can produce and secrete hormones. Some of rhizospheres bacterial are capable of nitrogen fixation free in the air and have another useful potential for plants, producing antibiotics, siderophores, can produce hormones (Halda and Alija, 2003).

Rhizosphere bacteria can produce plant growth hormones like auxins, cytokinins and gibberellins. The most frequently produced by microbes is indole-3 acetic acid (IAA) (Sutarya, 2011). Azotobacteria is one of the rhizobacteria that can bind atmospheric N, besides that Azotobacter is also able to synthesize growth hormone, namely IAA (Widiastuti et al., 2010). Azotobacter lives in the rhizosphere of plants and is widely used as a biological fertilizer (Hindersah et al., 2010). One of the Azotobacter species, *A. chroococcum*, is very beneficial for agricultural plants because of its ability to produce ammonia, vitamins, and growth substances which increase seed germination, production of indole acetic acid and other hormones, namely gibberellins and cytokinins (Mali & Bodhankar, 2009).

The use of chemical fertilizers in the long term causes a decrease in soil organic matter, damaged soil structure, and the environment. This is if it continues to decline in the quality of soil, water, environmental and human health. Therefore, an alternative to chemical fertilizers is needed, which can also increase agricultural production. One way is to use growth regulators produced by bacteria, which are more environmentally friendly. In this paper, we have discussed microbes that can be applied for more environmentally friendly agriculture.

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